

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CREATIVITY ORIENTED IN LEARNING RESEARCH AND DESIGN IN CLASSROOMS AND OUT-OF-CLASS ACTIVITIES BASED ON STEAM EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19435504>

Abstract. *It is necessary to improve school programs based on STEAM education, revise curricula and subjects, bring them into line with international standards, improve the quality of textbooks and literature, improve standards in higher education based on foreign experience, organize innovative activities for teachers, cultivate creativity aimed at educational research and design in classes and extracurricular activities, determine the stages of its formation as follows, and create a basis for students to develop imagination skills for sustainable, high-quality, low-cost, and sustainable living in real life, taking advantage of the available opportunities.*

Keywords: *program, approach, imagination, opportunity, integration, innovation, approximation, research, project training, creativity, foreign experience.*

Introduction

STEAM education in our country: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 5, 2018, PQ-5538 "On additional measures to improve the public education management system", In accordance with Resolution No. PQ-4199 of February 20, 2019 "On Measures for the Organization of Presidential Schools", Presidential schools for talented youth have been opened in each region of our country. In the Address of the President to the Oliy Majlis at the beginning of 2020, a number of issues were considered: improving school programs based on foreign experience, revising curriculum and subjects, bringing them into line with international standards, improving the quality of textbooks and literature, improving standards in higher education based on foreign experience, revising educational areas and subjects taught, and halving the number of non-specialized subjects.

STEAM education content: The demands of today's world pose great challenges in global education, that is, in preparing a child for life in society. At the same time, first of all, it is necessary to form among modern students the image of professionals who actively work in accordance with rapidly changing, updated information. The acquisition, processing, and application of information are the cornerstones of the STEAM curriculum. The term STEM: first introduced into the school curriculum in the United States, it aims to develop students' competencies in science and technology. Later, this series was expanded and additional letters were added to the term. In particular, "R" was added - robotics and "STRAIN" - or "A" - art, and it was called STEAM. This is (S - science, T - technology, E - engineering, A - art, M - mathematics) - a modern approach that combines science, technology, art and mathematics.

Integration (from Latin *integratio* - restoration, completion, integer - whole). Current science curricula challenge students to master a large number of concepts, which act as discrete

elements of knowledge. This creates difficulties in forming a holistic picture of the world, hinders the organic perception of culture, and becomes one of the reasons for the school graduate's fragmented worldview. Integration is the process and result of establishing interdisciplinary and interdisciplinary connections, achieving the integrity of educational content through interaction between different educational programs. In an integrated lesson, the subject of analysis is multifaceted objects, information about their essence is contained in various sources of information. The participation of teachers of relevant subjects in the organization of integrated lessons solves the psychological problem, which allows children to easily assimilate a new block of information, helps to increase the level of the teacher's general and professional culture, and helps to develop value orientations of schoolchildren from the point of view of global education.

Integrated extracurricular activities (projects, excursions, intellectual games). Integration in primary education can be divided into internal and external integration. In addition, innovative knowledge in physics, chemistry, and biology is provided through integration. The word "innovation" comes from Latin and means to introduce something new.

Innovative activity is the creation of a new technological process or a new improved product using scientific research, development, experimental work, or other scientific and technical achievements. Its pragmatic feature is that it is carried out neither in the field of ideas nor in the field of action of an individual subject, but is considered truly innovative only when the experience of implementing this activity becomes available to everyone in people's lives. The true essence of innovative activity is the formation of a new technology, the result of which is an activity aimed at transforming an invention that emerged as an innovation into a project, and a project into technology. The teacher can organize innovative activities and foster creativity focused on educational research and design in classroom and extracurricular activities, defining the stages of its formation as follows:

The first stage is the exact copying of the finished methodological recommendations. The second stage is when some new devices (modifications) and methods are introduced into the existing system. The third stage is when the content, methods, and form of implementing the new idea are fully developed. The fourth stage - the teacher develops his own concept and methodology of teaching and upbringing. When preparing teachers for innovative activities, it is necessary to take into account the psychological climate in the team and the extent to which team members are aware of innovations in the global education market. STEAM educational technology is based on a design approach and is based on cognitive and artistic inquiry. Such studies are carried out in the field of scientific research, acquiring knowledge in the process of practical activities, and then re-applying it in practice, that is, building structures in games using elements of technical creativity. STEAM education directly connects students' development to the outside world. As is known, natural sciences, technologies that are directly related to the world around us, are constantly used in our daily lives, and engineering is seen in homes, roads, bridges and cars, in professions, our daily knowledge is more or less dependent on mathematics.

Research materials and methodology

Relevance of the topic: A STEAM education-based approach allows young people to systematically explore the world, logically observe the processes taking place around them, discover new, unique, and interesting things for themselves, and understand their interconnections. By anticipating new things, the student becomes interested in learning, identifies an interesting problem for himself, develops an algorithm for finding a solution, critically evaluates the result, and develops engineering aspects of thinking.

Goals and objectives of the lesson: The main premise of the STEAM approach is that practice is as important as theoretical knowledge. At the same time, students must use not only their minds, but also their hands in the learning process. The learning process in the classroom has lagged behind the rapidly changing world. The main feature of the STEAM approach is that students use their minds and hands to effectively master many subjects, to "master" knowledge on their own. Students conduct experiments in the classroom, create models, create their own music and films, create robots, that is, implement their own ideas and create products. Because STEAM gives students the opportunity to apply what they learn in an educational environment, they will be faced with real-life problems as they grow up, such as environmental pollution, climate change, etc. problems, they only need to rely on their knowledge of different fields of science and work together. Relying on knowledge in one subject is not enough. Accordingly, the STEAM approach is also a way of thinking.

STEAM focuses on developing students' practical skills, which strengthens their collaboration, creativity, and willpower. Such knowledge and skills are the main task of education, and the entire education system strives for this. Many countries, including the US, Singapore, Korea, Australia, China, the UK, and Israel, have government programs in STEAM education. New types of jobs, as well as new areas of specialization, emerge every day, which must make today's educators think: Are the knowledge and skills of the students they are teaching up to date? STEAM education is highly valued in many countries for the following reasons: In recent years, the world has experienced a shortage of IT specialists, programmers, engineers, high-tech manufacturing specialists, and other similar professions; In the future, there will be professions that are difficult to imagine now, all of which are related to natural sciences, technology, and high-tech manufacturing. In particular, the need for specialists in bio and nanotechnology will increase; future specialists need comprehensive training and knowledge in various fields of education: natural sciences, engineering, and technology.

Search results

STEAM technology, unlike education, allows for the transfer of knowledge in a balanced manner, rather than in isolation. The student develops non-standard thinking, computational and creative abilities, which will be very useful in his future career. *The structure of the practical training* includes the procedure for performing the training and the names of the necessary educational equipment for its conduct. The student observes, identifies, and analyzes natural phenomena based on the assigned task. A separate hour is allocated for the practical training lesson. Before organizing the project work, the teacher develops a system of project work assignments. Students in the class, individually or in groups, independently collect information from various sources (textbook, Internet system) on the topic for a specified period of time, form the project structure, and conduct educational and research work. In project work, students plan the work, carry it out, draw conclusions, and make a presentation on the results of the work. Project work serves to develop proposals and develop creative activity in students.

The content of the practical assignment is represented by a list of equipment related to the topic of the lesson, text, pictures, graphs or tables related to the topic of the lesson. Students complete the assigned tasks using the recommended equipment, text, map, pictures, graphs and tables and present their conclusions. Practical assignments can be within the topics covered or cover interdisciplinary connections. The role of extracurricular activities, conferences, and evenings organized outside the classroom is invaluable in teaching students to think independently and work creatively. Extracurricular activities are a type of activity that is organized under the

direct supervision of a teacher, based on a plan, with a specific goal in mind, and taking into account the wishes of students. The goals and objectives of extracurricular activities are: To develop students' knowledge level and scientific outlook; To increase students' interest in science; To develop their specific characteristics in their work; To develop students' personal abilities; To form practical skills and qualifications in students; To direct students to a profession based on their abilities.

Project: Making a bridge out of pasta. Project goal: At least in real life, taking advantage of the opportunity to create a vision of durable, high-quality, low-cost, bridge-based living in students and to arouse interest in the professions of architecture, construction, and engineering. **Physics knowledge:** The student can correctly determine the center of mass, know and apply information about gravity, tension, and equilibrium conditions. **Mathematical knowledge:** The student can correctly select various geometric shapes and their sizes, paying attention to symmetry. Can perform calculations based on the selected shapes and drawings. **Look at the picture:** In 1292, Marco Polo brought pasta from China to Italy. But it is not known when it first appeared; Pasta is named after an entrepreneur named Marco Aro; In Italy, all pasta dishes are called "pasta" (dough for pasta).

Stage 1: Problem situation: Pose a problem to the listener and identify ways to solve it - What is the function of a bridge? Why is it necessary to build a bridge? What should be considered when building a quality bridge? What should be considered to build a strong bridge?

Stage 2: Technology of dividing the group into groups of 5. Professions: Physicist, Mathematician, Architect, Computer Scientist, Designer. **Working in groups: Stage 3: Each student contributes to the project work:** Searches for solutions to problems; Calculates raw materials; Creates a model; Compiles and presents an algorithm for the work to be done; Pays attention to aesthetics and advertising. **Requirements:** The length of the bridge must be at least 40 cm; The width of the bridge must be 10 cm; The construction of the bridge must cost a maximum of 15 thousand soums; The bridge must be able to carry a load weighing at least 5 kg; It must have an aesthetic appearance; It must be economical.

We will need:

**How are bridges made?
upper part**

intermediate support

last stand

The pasta bridge is ready

Troubleshooting: If any defects are observed in the bridge, if the bridge is leaning or its center of mass is incorrectly selected, they determine ways to eliminate it.

Questions: Why do you think a bridge is needed and what kind of work can be done with it? What do you think the bridge should look like? What is the importance of physics in completing this project? What is the importance of mathematics in completing this project? To evaluate the

prepared model, we can make a table in the following form. This table lists the aspects of the model and writes the scores assigned to it. *Evaluation*

Terms	Group name	Score
Model beauty		
Model durability		
Correct operation of the model		
Savings in model preparation		
Total points:		

Total points:

The main tasks of natural sciences are to develop a system of theoretical and practical knowledge about the essence, causes and interrelationships of phenomena and processes occurring in nature, the stages of development of nature, including the evolution of living organisms, the natural scientific foundations of modern technology and equipment, the interrelationship and influence of nature and society, the scientific foundations of the economical use of natural resources, the principles of effective management and control of economic processes, and the essence and importance of a healthy lifestyle.

A student's intrinsic motivation plays an important role in their interest in mastering natural sciences, their ability to understand the state of the natural and social environment through them, their ability to understand environmental and human problems, and their ability to make decisions to find solutions to them. The integration of disciplines creates a basis for students to perceive nature as a whole, and for the emergence of a single natural-scientific picture of the world in their thinking. At the same time, interdisciplinary integration is aimed at developing in students an understanding of the opportunities and problems of modern scientific and technological progress, the essence of environmental problems, ways of rational use of nature, and the principles of adhering to a healthy lifestyle, and the skills to use them in everyday life.

Based on STEAM education, it aims to develop students' interest in conducting educational research, conducting experiments, and designing-oriented creativity in the natural sciences, demonstrating the relevance of their acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies to everyday life, and developing their interest in creating innovations. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to instill in the minds of the younger generation practical exercises, laboratory work, and practical tasks that encourage independent performance and creative thinking, designed to work with tasks that meet the requirements of the international assessment program (PISA, TIMSS) aimed at developing students' logical thinking and practical skills.

Conclusion and recommendations

In teaching natural sciences, not only their internal integration with each other, but also their external integration with related disciplines is of great importance. In particular, their close interaction with the following scientific areas is important:

Competencies formed through native language and reading subjects play an important role in teaching natural sciences in developing students' creative thinking, developing the skills to express their views fluently in writing and orally, using scientific terms correctly, and teaching them to communicate freely in the process of debate.

The skills taught in the subject of mathematics are important for solving problems related to mathematical measurements and calculations in natural science classes, finding the most optimal solution, and making the right decisions during laboratory and other experiments.

Informatics and information technology create enormous opportunities for improving the efficiency of the teaching process of natural sciences through the use of various forms of information and communication technologies and computer equipment.

The competencies acquired through the subject of technology are of high professional importance in the process of teaching natural sciences, in guiding students towards a profession, developing their technical creative abilities, and in forming the skills to prepare creative projects. The natural sciences subject forms scientific and practical concepts in students about natural and socio-economic objects, processes and phenomena, the natural conditions and resources of our Motherland, its population and economy, the geographical foundations of the relationship between nature and man, global and regional problems of rational use and protection of nature, teaches independent thinking, and the practical application of geographical knowledge. In the process of teaching science, special attention is paid to the formation of students' skills in using maps and ecological literacy. At the same time, the concepts and competencies formed as a result of teaching primary school natural sciences serve to form a comprehensive picture of the objects, phenomena, and processes studied in other natural sciences.

Biology subjects form in students a sense of the objects and systems of living nature, the connections between living and inanimate nature. They acquire skills in solving problems of the living environment, and the socialization of students improves. At the same time, a positive attitude towards the living nature surrounding us, preserving natural diversity, as well as a strong sense of responsibility are formed. As a recommendation, STEAM education should enable students to acquire the scientific awareness competency of planning, designing, and proposing methods for conducting various studies on natural phenomena and processes observed in everyday life. As a practical competency, we need to educate students to independently master the skills of observing events, conducting presentations, experiments and projects, measuring necessary quantities using instruments (stopwatch, scales, measuring tape, thermometer, etc.), performing calculations, observing safety rules and using them rationally when using various equipment, knowing the factors that negatively affect the environment and ecology, thinking creatively and logically in daily activities, consciously planning their intellectual development, and monitoring and evaluating the results of their educational activities.

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